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Research Article

**EFFECTS OF ASCORBIC ACID ON SOME CLINICAL
CHEMISTRY PARAMETERS OF MALE RABBITS**Amani. M. M. Salem¹, Sundis. A. A. Albera², Fayrouz. A. Khaled²¹Biomedical Science Department, Faculty of pharmacy, Omar Al-Mokhtar University, El - Beida-Libya²Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Omar Al-Mokhtar University, El -Beida-Libya

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Abstract:

Ascorbic acid is a basic micronutrient required for typical metabolic pathways on the body. Ascorbic acid (AA) has a key role on the primary action of anti-oxidant resistance framework against stress factors, especially oxidative stress. We have therefore investigated the effects of either 40 mg/kg B.W. doses of ascorbic acid on the levels of biochemical parameters in male New Zealand White rabbits. Animals were orally given 40 mg/kg B.W. The tested doses were given to rabbits every other day for 10 weeks. Treatment with ascorbic acid caused significant ($P < 0:05$) decrease in the concentrations of plasma asparatate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP) and acid phosphatase (AcP) activities. Contrariwise, the total protein (TP), globulin and albumin were significantly increased in plasma. While, did not change the levels of glucose. Concentrations of urea, creatinine, total lipid (TL), cholesterol, triglycerides (TG), low density lipoprotein (LDL) and very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) were significantly decreased, while high density lipoprotein (HDL) was increased.

Keywords: Ascorbic acid, Anti-oxidant, Biochemistry, Rabbits**Corresponding author:****Amani. M. M. Salem,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Vitamin C (also known as ascorbic acid and ascorbate) is a vitamin found in various foods and sold as a dietary supplement.¹ It is used to prevent and treat scurvy¹. Vitamin C is an essential nutrient involved in the repair of tissue and the enzymatic production of certain neurotransmitters². It is required for the functioning of several enzymes and is important for immune system function³. It also functions as an antioxidant⁴. Ascorbic acid is one of the most effective, powerful antioxidants in biological fluids. Vitamin C scavenges physiologically important reactive oxygen species such as superoxide radical anion, hydrogen peroxide, hydroxyl radical and singlet oxygen, and also reactive nitrogen species⁵. It regenerates other small molecule antioxidants such as α -tocopherol, reduced glutathione, urate, and β -carotene from their respective radical species and may, therefore, prevent oxidative damage to biological macromolecules, including DNA, lipids, and proteins⁶. Vitamin C is structurally similar to glucose and hence possibly may replace it in many chemical reactions, such as non-enzymatic glycosylation of proteins (Maillard reactions).

Vitamin C was reported to attenuate hepatic damage induced by some chemical agents especially in animals. This is supported by the work of⁷. They reported that vitamin C normalized levels of alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, alkaline phosphatase, blood hydroperoxide and malondialdehyde in liver of carbon tetrachloride intoxicated rats. The ability of vitamin C to prevent Carbon tetrachloride induced hepatotoxicity in rats was also reported by many previous studies^{8,9}.

Ascorbic acid reduced cypermethrin induced Cytotoxicity in rat hepatocytes by recovering 60% of glutathione and 54% decrease in gamma glutamyl transpeptidase. Ascorbic acid was also able to preserved 100% of cell integrity and modulated alanine aminotransferase and aspartate aminotransferase¹⁰. Similar observation was reported when deltamethrin (1.28 mg/kg) was administered to wistar rats. Alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, alkaline phosphatase and gamma glutamyl transpeptidase were significantly increased. Pretreatment with vitamin C (200 mg/kg) normalized the above mentioned parameters¹¹. The hepatoprotective effect of vitamin C against organophosphate induced liver damage can be further buttressed by the findings of¹². He and his co-researchers exposed rats to a mixture of organophosphate

insecticides for 28 days. This induced liver toxicity via elevated levels of serum aspartate aminotransferase, Alanine aminotransferase, alkaline phosphatase and disruption of liver structure. Vitamin C supplementation was reported to attenuate the hepatotoxic effects induced by the mixture of organophosphate insecticides. Dietary vitamin C supplement may have protective effect on the liver and also improve hepatic function as reported by some researchers. This is supported by findings from the evaluation of vitamin C on lipid peroxidation and glutathione system in the normal guinea pig heart. It was observed that dietary vitamin C supplementation is able to increase global antioxidant capacity of guinea pig heart tissues¹³. Dietary vitamin C supplement was also reported to confer protective effect against endotoxin induced oxidative damage to protein in guinea pig liver. This seems mainly due to a direct increase in hepatic ascorbate levels in vitamin C exposed animals¹⁴. Dietary vitamin C supplement was reported to decrease endogenous protein oxidative damage and lipid peroxidation in the guinea pig liver¹⁵. Further study showed that administration of monosodium glutamate (food additive) at a dose level of 0.6, 6 and 60 mg/kg for 14 days increased serum alanine aminotransferase and aspartate aminotransferase dose dependently. These elevated parameters were reduced after pretreatment with vitamin C. Histopathological changes induced by monosodium glutamate were also ameliorated¹⁶.

The molecular mechanisms of the antiscorbutic effect of Vitamin C are largely, although not completely, understood¹⁷. Vitamin C is a cofactor for several enzymes involved in the biosynthesis of collagen, carnitine, and neurotransmitters^{18,19}. In addition, Vitamin C is used as a cofactor for catecholamine biosynthesis, in particular the conversion of dopamine to norepinephrine catalysed by dopamine β -monooxygenase¹⁸. The activities of several other enzymes are known to be dependent on Vitamin C, although their connection to scurvy has not yet been clearly established. These enzymes include the mono- and dioxygenases involved in peptide amidation and tyrosine metabolism. Vitamin C has also been implicated in the metabolism of cholesterol to bile acids via the enzyme cholesterol 7-monooxygenase and in steroid metabolism in the adrenals^{18,19}. Hydroxylation of aromatic drugs and carcinogens by hepatic cytochrome P450 is also enhanced by reducing agents such as Vitamin C¹⁹. Also, Vitamin C is an important water-soluble antioxidant in biological fluids. Even small amounts vitamin C can protect indispensable molecules in the body, such as proteins, lipids (fats), carbohydrates, and nucleic acids (DNA

and RNA) from damage by free radicals and reactive oxygen species that can be generated during normal metabolism as well as through exposure to toxins and pollutants. Vitamin C may also be able to regenerate other antioxidants such as vitamin E¹⁷.

Hypercholesterolemia is one of the major risk factors of atherosclerosis. Many prospective epidemiologic studies have found a continuous graded, direct relationship between total serum cholesterol level and the incidence of coronary heart disease²⁰.

LDL is the primary transporter of cholesterol in the blood; consequently, total cholesterol levels and LDL cholesterol levels are highly correlated. LDL cholesterol is a risk factor for atherogenesis and coronary heart disease (CHD). When LDL is oxidized, it is taken up by endothelial cells and macrophages in the arterial wall, leading to the first stages of atherosclerosis (fatty streaks). Antioxidants such as vitamin C are now being investigated in clinical trials exploring prevention of CHD²¹. Vitamin C could react rapidly with O₂ to play an antioxidant role in cytosol and extracellular matrix. It has been reported that vitamin C also scavenges peroxynitrite very effectively to prevent the formations of nitrotyrosine, nitrotryptophan and nitrated lipids²². In addition, intra-arterial administration of high dose of vitamin C results in improved vasodilation in hypertensive patients²³.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In this study ascorbic acid (Vitamin C, liquid supplement) was used. Ascorbic acid (AA, 20%) was purchased from Neofarma, Italy (Via Emilia Km 18, n.1854-47020 Longiano, Fo, Italy). The dose of AA was 40 mg/kg body weight (BW) every other day. This dose was used because the previous studies showed that 20 or 40 mg AA/kg BW afforded comparatively more significant amelioration against pesticides, but the lower dose (10 mg/kg BW per day) of AA (quantitatively equivalent to the human therapeutic dose according to body weight) was least efficacious²⁴. Also²⁵, showed that treatment with 20 mg/kg BW on hematological parameters. Therefore in this study we suggest to use 40 mg AA not 20 mg AA/kg BW per every other day.

Mature male New Zealand White rabbits age of 6 months and initial weight of (2.978 ± 0.07 Kg) were used. Ten mature male rabbits were randomly divided into couple equal groups (each five rabbits): Group I: Rabbits were used as control successive weeks. Group II: Rabbits were treated with ascorbic acid. Ascorbic acid was given daily by gavage at a dose of 40 mg/kg BW for 10 successive weeks. At the end of the

experimental period, all rabbits were weighed then sacrificed under ether anesthesia. Blood samples were collected in clean dry centrifuge tubes. Plasma was separated by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes and then quickly frozen at -20°C for biochemical parameters analysis.

Plasma was obtained by centrifugation of samples at 860 xg for 20 min, and was stored at -20°C until used for analyses. Stored plasma samples were analyzed for total protein (TP) by the Biuret method according to²⁶. Albumin (A) concentration was determined by the method of²⁷. Plasma glucose, urea and creatinine concentrations were measured by the method of^{28,29}, respectively. Plasma concentrations of total lipids, cholesterol and triglycerides (TG) were determined according to the methods of^{30,31,32}, respectively. High-density lipoprotein (HDL) was determined according to the methods of³³. Low-density lipoprotein (LDL) was determined by the calculation (cholesterol-(TG/5+HDL)). Very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) was calculated by dividing the values of TG by factor of 5.

The activities of plasma aspartate transaminase (AST; EC 2.6.1.1) and alanine transaminase (ALT; EC 2.6.1.2) were assayed according to the procedure of³⁴. Alkaline phosphatase (ALP; EC 3.1.3.1) activity was determined in plasma according to the method of³⁵. Acid phosphatase (AcP; EC 3.1.3.2) activity was determined according to the method of³⁶.

Statistical analysis:

Data were analyzed according to³⁷. Statistical significance of the difference in values of control and treated animals was calculated by F test with 5% significance level. Data of the present study were statistically analyzed by using Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

RESULTS:

Data represented in Table 1,2 and 3 showed that Treatment with ascorbic acid caused significant (P < 0:05) decrease in the concentrations of plasma aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP) and acid phosphatase (AcP) activities. Contrariwise, the total protein (TP), globulin and albumin was significantly increased in plasma. While, did not change the levels of glucose. In contrast, Concentrations of urea, creatinine, total lipid (TL) cholesterol, triglycerides (TG), low density lipoprotein (LDL) and very low density lipoprotein (VLDL) were significantly decreased, while high density lipoprotein (HDL) was increased.

Table 1. The overall means ($\pm$ S.E.) of plasma aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), alkaline phosphatase (AIP) and acid phosphatase during treatment of male rabbits with ascorbic acid (AA).

Parameters	Animal Groups	
	Control	Ascorbic acid
AST (U/L)	27.0 $\pm$ 0.96 ^b	29.1 $\pm$ 1.02 ^b
ALT(U/L)	15.5 $\pm$ 0.34 ^c	16.3 $\pm$ 0.5 ^{cb}
AIP(U/L)	73.0 $\pm$ 4.49 ^b	76.1 $\pm$ 2.20 ^b
AcP (U/L)	11.1 $\pm$ 0.47 ^c	13.0 $\pm$ 0.63 ^b

Values are expressed as means $\pm$ SE; n=5 for each treatment group. Mean values within a row not sharing a common superscript letter (a, b, c, d) were significantly different, $p < 0.05$.

Table 2. The overall means ($\pm$ S.E.) of plasma total protein (TP), globulin, albumin, glucose, urea and creatinine during treatment of male rabbits with ascorbic acid (AA).

Parameters	Animal Groups	
	Control	Ascorbic acid
TP(g/dl)	8.1 $\pm$ 0.20 ^a	7.8 $\pm$ 0.18 ^a
Globulin(g/dl)	3.2 $\pm$ 0.17 ^a	3.1 $\pm$ 0.16 ^a
Albumin(g/dl)	4.9 $\pm$ 0.14 ^a	4.9 $\pm$ 0.13 ^a
Glucose (mg/dl)	108.9 $\pm$ 4.60 ^c	107.9 $\pm$ 3.51 ^c
Urea (mg/dl)	51.0 $\pm$ 1.13 ^b	44.9 $\pm$ 0.91 ^c
Creatinine(mg/dl)	1.3 $\pm$ 0.06 ^a	1.1 $\pm$ 0.07 ^a

Values are expressed as means $\pm$ SE; n=5 for each treatment group. Mean values within a row not sharing a common superscript letter (a, b, c, d) were significantly different, $p < 0.05$.

Table 3. The overall means ($\pm$ S.E.) of plasma total lipid (TL), cholesterol, triglycerides (TG), low density lipoprotein (LDL), high density lipoprotein (HDL) and very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) during treatment of male rabbits with ascorbic acid (AA).

Parameters (mg/dl)	Animal Groups	
	Control	Ascorbic acid
TL	386 $\pm$ 12.03 ^{ab}	365.7 $\pm$ 9.09 ^b
Cholesterol	85.0 $\pm$ 0.78 ^c	84.2 $\pm$ 1.05 ^{cb}
TG	48.6 $\pm$ 3.48 ^b	36.4 $\pm$ 1.19 ^c
LDL	56.1 $\pm$ 1.44 ^c	55.5 $\pm$ 0.75 ^c
HDL	21.1 $\pm$ 1.13 ^a	22.6 $\pm$ 0.65 ^a
VLDL	10.0 $\pm$ 0.64 ^b	7.4 $\pm$ 0.35 ^c

Values are expressed as means $\pm$ SE; n=5 for each treatment group. Mean values within a row not sharing a common superscript letter (a, b, c, d) were significantly different, $p < 0.05$.

DISCUSSION:

Antioxidants are known to reduce oxidative-radical induced reactions. Vitamin C is an essential dietary nutrient required as a co-factor for many enzymes, and humans are among the few animals that lack the ability to synthesis the compound from glucose. The reduced form of the vitamin, ascorbic acid, is an especially effective antioxidant owing to its high electron-donating power and ready conversion back to the active reduced form. There is great interest in the clinical roles of Vitamin C because of evidence that oxidative damage is a root cause of, or at least associated with, many diseases. Population studies show that individuals with high intakes of Vitamin C have lower risk of a number of chronic diseases, including heart disease, cancer, eye diseases, and neurodegenerative conditions. The evidence that ascorbic acid acts as an important antioxidant in many body tissues is convincing³⁸.

³⁹ reported that greater dietary Vitamin C (100 and 200 mg/kg of diet) resulted in a decrease in serum glucose, urea, triglycerides, and cholesterol concentrations, while protein and albumin concentrations increased when dietary Vitamin C was increased in Japanese quails. Vitamin C. Also, ⁴⁰ found that rabbits treated with AA (20 mg/kg BW) showed increase in haematological parameters and decrease in plasma cholesterol. Also, they reported that there was no changes in the concentrations of urea, creatinine, glucose and bilirubin, and the activities of AST, ALT and AIP. ⁴⁰ ³⁹ reported that greater dietary vitamin C resulted in an increase in total protein and albumin concentrations in Japanese quails.

The presence of ascorbic acid reduced the levels of urea (Table 4). These results are in agreement with the previous studies of^{40,41,42}. Also, ³⁹ reported that vitamin C resulted in a decrease in serum glucose and urea. Vitamin C is nonessential suppressors which have ability to decrease lipid peroxidation then forage free radicals⁴³. Vitamin C plays a role in steroid production in metal-exposed rats that decline physiological strain associated injury in sperm formation⁴⁴.⁴⁵ Simon and Hudes suggested that vitamin C involved in the metabolism of cholesterol to bile acids, which may have implications for blood cholesterol levels and the incidence of gallstones. The

present study showed that AA caused a decrease in the lipid profile. Also, ³⁹ reported that greater dietary vitamin C (100 and 200 mg/kg of diet) resulted in a decrease in serum triglycerides and cholesterol concentrations. In addition, the cholesterol levels of people who took 1500 mg of vita-min C a day. This was found to encourage the conversion of cholesterol into bile acids, which are then eliminated from the body in the feces. Similarly, several animal studies indicated that vitamin C contributes to this conversion by stimulating an enzyme that regulates the process⁴⁶.

CONCLUSION:

Ascorbic acid is needed for various metabolic pathways and functions in the body. Ascorbic acid acts as an antioxidant agent, which can protective the hepatic, and maintaining the activity of biochemical and hematological parameters.

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